

QRSA: Architecture for Quantum-safe 5G

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ABSTRACT

The evolving 5G architecture, moving from proprietary monolithic hardware towards the disaggregated and modular Open Radio Access Network (Open RAN), introduces new, critical interfaces requiring robust security. While IPsec is a prevalent solution for securing IP communications, the advent of quantum computing threatens its traditional cryptographic underpinnings; it may be deprecated in the near future. To address this, we propose a quantum-safe Open RAN framework for securing fronthaul (i.e., Radio Unit-Distributed Unit) and backhaul (i.e., Centralized Unit-5G core) interfaces. Our framework employs a hybrid key exchange scheme, combining post-quantum cryptography (PQC) with quantum keys as cryptographic material, designed for seamless integration with TLS, IKEv2/IPsec, and MACsec standards, and compatible with ETSI QKD 004 and 014 APIs. Furthermore, we present a novel key distribution protocol for Quantum Key Distribution Networks (QKDN). This protocol incorporates encapsulation techniques inspired by onion routing, combined with PQC, to ensure confidentiality, integrity, authenticity, and anonymity. It also leverages post-quantum public key encryption to protect shared secrets from intermediate nodes within the QKDN, mitigating intermediary attacks. We have deployed a proof-of-concept of our proposal, experimentally validating both air-based and fiber-based QKD, primarily using ML-KEM and ML-DSA standards for PQC algorithms.

Keywords: QKD, IPsec, PQC, ETSI 004 API, ETSI 014 API

1. INTRODUCTION

The digital era has driven an unprecedented evolution in communications, with 5G networks¹ emerging as a cornerstone for the next generation of connectivity. Beyond offering ultra-fast speeds (up to 10 gigabits per second, a hundred times faster than 4G) and minimal latency, 5G is a driver of hyper-connectivity, enabling a massive number of simultaneously connected devices and previously unthinkable capabilities. Its transformative impact spans multiple industries² and applications, from telehealth and high-precision remote surgery to the automotive sector with autonomous vehicles, Industry 4.0 with digital twins and supply chain management, and the development of smart cities.

In this context of technological progress, the Open RAN (Radio Access Network) architecture is a key innovation for the deployment of 5G networks.³ Open RAN⁴ promotes the disaggregation of hardware and software, enabling interoperability between components from different vendors. This translates into a significant reduction in implementation and operation costs, greater agility in innovation by simplifying the integration of new technologies, and a diversification of suppliers that fosters competition and avoids dependence on a single manufacturer. Open RAN's flexibility and modularity make it a strategic solution for optimizing network operations, deploying services faster and scaling the infrastructure according to market needs.

Nevertheless, alongside these advances, a growing threat is emerging: quantum computing. Quantum computers, which are still under development, suppose an exponential processing power that could break current classic cryptographic algorithms.⁵ These algorithms are the basis for the security of our communications and data, according to experts in the field, the advent of quantum computers capable of breaching current cryptographic systems is imminent. This poses a significant cybersecurity risk, as encrypted data could be compromised

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if organizations do not adopt post-quantum protection technologies. Preparing for this transition is of the utmost importance. It requires advance planning and investment in new cryptographic capabilities.

In light of these developments, the QURSA⁶ (QUantum-based Resistant Architectures and Techniques) project has been initiated to address the security challenges posed by quantum computing in communication networks, particularly in the context of 5G networks and beyond. The QURSA project is dedicated to the development of architectures and techniques that are resilient to quantum attacks. This initiative encompasses the exploration of quantum key distribution (QKD) in software-defined networks (SDNs) and post-quantum security. The objective is to implement and evaluate post-quantum cryptography in relevant application scenarios. QURSA is a foundational initiative to safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of communications in the post-quantum era.

2. OPEN RAN

The Open RAN architecture is a significant development in the field of radio access networks, characterized by the disaggregation of their components. A key element in this transformation is the Baseband Unit (BBU). The BBU functions, which have historically been monolithic, are divided into the following components in Open RAN: the Radio Unit (RU) for RF and Low-PHY functions, the Distributed Unit (DU) for High-PHY, MAC and RLC, and the Centralized Unit (CU) for control plane functions. This disaggregation⁷ allows for the use of general-purpose hardware, offering greater flexibility and scalability while breaking the dependency on proprietary solutions.

Interoperability in Open RAN is achieved by standardizing the interfaces⁸ between these disaggregated units. The following critical interfaces should be noted: the Fronthaul (between RU and DU), which carries physical layer data and has been standardized by the O-RAN Alliance to optimize traffic; the Midhaul (between DU and CU), which connects these units and corresponds to the 3GPP F1 interface; and the Backhaul (between CU and the Core network), which links the CU to the core network and corresponds to the 3GPP NG interface.

While these open interfaces undoubtedly bring flexibility and innovation, they also introduce new security challenges⁹ that require proactive attention. The disaggregation of components and the involvement of multiple vendors increase the attack surface of the network. Securing these interfaces is imperative, as they facilitate the flow of sensitive data, telemetry, and control commands. Vulnerabilities could compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the network, so it is crucial to implement robust cryptographic protection, mutual authentication, and communication integrity protection mechanisms to ensure that Open RAN implementations are intrinsically secure.¹⁰

3. SECURITY IN OPEN RAN

Security in Open RAN¹¹ is fundamental to ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of communications between User Equipments (UEs) and the 5G core. Traditionally, the protection of the fronthaul, midhaul, and backhaul segments has relied on a set of standard security mechanisms.

The fronthaul has historically been a sensitive segment due to the nature of the radio frequency signal. In traditional architectures and CPRI (Common Public Radio Interface) implementations, security has largely focused on the physical security of the link (dedicated optical fiber or protected microwave links) and network segmentation. The logic that a dedicated interface is inherently secure if physically protected has been predominant. However, with the evolution towards Open RAN and Ethernet-based fronthauls, the need for Layer 2 encryption¹² and authentication, such as MACsec (IEEE 802.1AE¹³), has become more critical. MACsec provides data confidentiality, integrity, and protection against replay attacks on the physical or logical link.

In the case of the midhaul has generally been designed over IP/MPLS infrastructures. Security in this segment is often achieved through the use of Virtual Private Networks (VPNs).¹⁴ IPsec-based VPNs are common for establishing secure tunnels that encrypt and authenticate data traffic, protecting it from unauthorized access as it pass through intermediate networks. Network-level security can also be reinforced with firewalls and network segmentation to control traffic flow and access between the DU and the CU.

Lastly, the backhaul is usually the segment with the highest capacity and, therefore, has already implemented the most mature security solutions.¹⁵ Here, protection relies on a combination of IPsec VPNs for end-to-end

encryption and TLS (Transport Layer Security) for securing applications and signaling protocols. Strong device authentication, perimeter firewalls, and intrusion detection are also fundamental for backhaul security.

4. PQC, QKD AND HYBRID SOLUTIONS

As quantum computing advances, two main approaches to securing communications in the post-quantum era are emerging: Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). On the one hand, PQC¹⁶ refers to cryptographic algorithms designed to run on classical computers, but which are resistant to attack by future quantum computers. These algorithms are based on complex mathematical problems that are considered secure even against quantum machines, such as those based on lattices, ciphers or hash functions, and are being standardized by entities such as NIST.¹⁷ On the other hand, QKD¹⁸ is a secure method of key exchange that uses the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics, such as superposition and entanglement, to ensure that any attempt at eavesdropping is detectable. Its security lies in the laws of quantum physics, making it theoretically “unconditionally secure” against any attacker, including quantum computers, although it requires dedicated hardware and is sensitive to distance.

To facilitate the adoption of QKD and ensure its interoperability and compatibility with existing infrastructures, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has developed key specifications through its Industry Specification Group for Quantum Key Distribution (ISG-QKD).¹⁹ An example of this is the ETSI GS QKD 004 specification,²⁰ which defines application interfaces for QKD systems, known as Key Delivery APIs, providing an abstraction layer that facilitates the delivery of quantum keys to classical security applications. Additionally, the ETSI GS QKD 014²¹ specification focuses on the delivery of secure keys in optical networks and is compatible with network architectures such as SDN, facilitating their deployment.

Given the complementary nature of the two approaches, hybridization of PQC and QKD emerges as an optimal strategy for securing communications over the long term. This combination leverages the strengths of each technology: PQC offers the flexibility to be deployed on existing network infrastructure and protect a wide range of applications, while QKD provides a physical key security layer that is immune to computational advances. Hybridization enables the creation of a multi-layer defense, where keys can be derived from multiple sources²² (PQC, QKD and even classical cryptography), ensuring that even if one method of key exchange were to be compromised, the final hybrid key maintains its security thanks to the redundancy provided by the other sources. The synergy between PQC and QKD is key to building robust communication infrastructures ready for the quantum future. Projects such as QURSA, precisely, explore this combination, investigating both QKD in SDN and post-quantum security to develop architectures and techniques resistant to quantum attacks. The synergy between PQC and QKD is key to building robust communication infrastructures ready for the quantum future.

5. QUANTUM-SAFE OPEN RAN

Recognizing that Open RAN introduces new interfaces and potential vulnerabilities, in the QURSA project it has been developed hybrid PQC/QKD solutions to protect the link, network, and transport communications within this environment, leveraging advancements in MACsec, IPsec, and TLS; already applying some of these solutions in realistic environments using software provided by srsRAN.²³

For the data link layer (Layer 2), QURSA has proposed enhancements to MACsec, enabling the renewal of keys generated through QKD or PQC. This is particularly relevant in the Open RAN fronthaul, where point-to-point link protection is crucial. Key management is performed via Key Management Entities (KMEs), which periodically update the pre-shared keys (PSK) using both QKD and PQC-KEM (Key Encapsulation Mechanism), for instance, utilizing CRYSTALS-Kyber. Each option its necessary depending on the fronthaul’s length and the available hardware.

At the network layer (Layer 3), QURSA has focused on improving the IPsec protocol suite, commonly used in VPNs. The first phase of key exchange (IKEv2) has been modified in the strongSwan open-source project, replacing classic Diffie-Hellman algorithms with PQC-KEM, QKD, or even hybridizations of both.²⁴ This ensures quantum-safe communication for the underlying IP infrastructure of Open RAN, including midhaul and backhaul, even before the establishment of virtualized network services.

Figure 1. Open RAN secured topology

For the transport layer (Layer 4), QURSA has addressed the Transport Layer Security protocol (TLS). A hybrid QKD-KEM solution²⁵ has been designed for TLS, implemented in OpenSSL. This developed version of TLS is essential not only for protecting communications in the Open RAN backhaul but also, fundamentally, for securing calls to QKD nodes, which are based on ETSI standardized key requests operating over HTTPS.

Finally, it is worth mention a parallel QURSA’s solution to distribute quantum keys even in scenarios where the distances between network points are large, rendering point-to-point QKD unfeasible. If all sites are located within the same Quantum Key Distribution Network (QKDN), QURSA has implemented a hybrid QKD/PQC solution that enhances key distribution security by applying Onion Routing.²⁶ This allows MACsec, IPsec, or TLS endpoints to utilize QKD keys, even if they are not directly quantum-connected, thereby extending the reach of quantum security across the distributed Open RAN infrastructure.

To demonstrate the feasibility of the solutions proposed by QURSA, a realistic Open RAN topology scenario was created using open-source projects such as srsRAN, Open5GS, and UERANSIM. As shown in Figure 1, each interface was protected with the quantum-safe mechanisms described in this section taking advantage that each element of the topology has access to a QKDN, allowing QKD keys to be used between them. Specifically, QKD/PQC-MACsec was implemented on the Fronthaul interface by UVIGO, QKD/PQC-TLS was implemented by UC3M, and QKD/PQC-IPsec was a joint effort between the two universities.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The rise of quantum computing poses an imminent threat to current communication infrastructures, including next-generation access networks like Open RAN. While Open RAN offers unprecedented flexibility through its disaggregated and open interfaces, it simultaneously introduces new attack vectors that demand proactive addressing with quantum-resistant solutions. The work presented in this study, under the QURSA project, underscores the commitment to developing robust security for Open RAN architectures in the post-quantum era. We have demonstrated how a layered security approach, integrating PQC and QKD, can be effectively applied across Open RAN segments, notably through hybrid PQC/QKD implementations for MACsec in fronthaul, IPsec for midhaul and backhaul, and TLS for transport layer protocols and even the backhaul. QURSA’s developments provide a comprehensive framework and concrete solutions to fortify Open RAN’s security against future quantum threats, ensuring the resilience and trustworthiness of next-generation mobile networks.

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